

DENTAL CARIES

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Abstract: "Toothache" is a word that scares children and adults, men and women. Caries is one of the main causes of severe pain in the teeth. This disease can be dangerous in different degrees, but it must be treated in any case. In the article, we will talk about the most effective methods of caries treatment, as well as the prevention of the disease.

Key words: tooth, caries, oral, hole, teeth, pain, worm

Caries is one of the most common diseases of the oral cavity. When caries occurs, the tooth enamel is damaged first, and if left untreated, it damages the dentin (the hard tissue of the tooth). Caries is derived from the Latin language and means "rotting". Caries is popularly known by the terms "tooth decay" and "tooth worm", the use of the second term is slightly incorrect from the point of view of medicine. The first sign of caries is the appearance of black spots on tooth enamel. If these spots are not paid attention to, the diameter of the caries may increase and the pathology may spread deeper into the tooth tissue and create a "hole". When caries breaks through the tooth enamel and dentin, it reaches the pulp (soft tissue of the tooth) and can cause severe pain. Inflammation of the pulp is called pulpitis.

Depending on the degree of damage to the tooth, caries are divided into spots (discoloration of the tooth surface), superficial caries (surface damage), medium caries (the upper part of the dentin is damaged) and deep caries (the dentin is almost completely damaged and has reached the pulp). In addition, caries of enamel, dentine and root cement are classified separately - in root cement caries, the disease appears under the gums.

Stages of dental caries

Depending on the place of occurrence, fissure (occurs in the cavity of the tooth), proximal (between the teeth) and cervical caries (near or below the gums) are classified. In addition, there are caries of the front teeth, which have a negative effect on the aesthetics of the smile. Usually, when the front teeth are damaged, even those who are afraid of dentists immediately turn to them.

In order to avoid a visit to the dentist, you need to independently examine the oral cavity. If you detect caries at an early stage, you can stop it even without the help of a dentist.

SYMPTOMS OF DENTAL CARIES

It is very easy to determine if you have tooth decay. A change in the color of the tooth surface (the stain can be dark or liquid) or its structure, for example, roughness, are symptoms that indicate the occurrence of the disease. Also, toothache when eating, especially strong pain that occurs under the influence of sweet, hot and cold, is also a sign of caries. A bad smell from the mouth can also be a symptom of the disease.

If the disease has progressed to the middle stage, a cavity has appeared in the tooth - usually it is easily felt with the tongue. However, the "hole" does not occur only because of caries, the exact diagnosis can only be made by a dentist.

CAUSES OF CARIES

The main cause of caries (tooth decay) is acid-producing bacteria that leach fluoride and calcium from tooth tissue. Microorganisms begin to multiply and damage the tooth 1-2 hours after cleaning the oral cavity, causing tooth decay.

Lack of salivation can also contribute to the development of caries. In fact, the mineral substances of saliva are able to partially eliminate the acids produced by bacteria. When saliva is produced too little, the acids begin to erode the teeth quickly. In addition, saliva partially washes away wrinkles. Xerostomia ("dryness" in the mouth) can develop as a result of various diseases, for example, diabetes, hypertension, nasal breathing disorders.

In addition, tooth decay can also be caused by frequent consumption of sweets, and this depends not on how much glucose is consumed, but on how long it is in contact with the teeth, that is, how long it "sticks" to the teeth. . Improper nutrition affects not only the teeth, but also the health of the oral cavity as a whole. Also, caries can develop due to a malfunction of the immune system, among other factors. The reason for the breakdown can be stress. Stress can also slow down mineralization processes in the oral cavity.

If caries is detected, you should change your diet, pay more attention to oral hygiene, and give preference to toothpastes with a high content of calcium and fluoride. A visit to the dentist is mandatory. Only timely treatment of caries helps to save teeth.

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